

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Scalable full-cycle marine litter remediation in the Mediterranean: Robotic and participatory solutions

SeaClear2.0

<https://www.seaclear2.eu>

D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan

WP6 – Public engagement, policy, dissemination

Grant Agreement no. 101093822

Lead beneficiary: Regional agency DUNEA

Date: 30/06/2023

Type: R

Dissemination level: PU

SeaClear2.0 is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101093822). Views and opinions expressed herein are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Document information

Grant agreement no.	101093822
Acronym:	SeaClear2.0
Full title:	Scalable full-cycle marine litter remediation in the Mediterranean: Robotic and participatory solutions
Start date of the project	01/01/2023
Duration of the project	48 months
Deliverable	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan
Work package	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination
Deliverable leader	Regional agency DUNEA
Delivery date	Contractual: 30/06/2023 Actual: 26/06/2023
Status	Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Type¹	R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DEM <input type="checkbox"/> OTHER <input type="checkbox"/> DMP <input type="checkbox"/>
Dissemination level²	PU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> C-UE/EU-C <input type="checkbox"/> SEN <input type="checkbox"/>
Author(s)	Iva Pozniak (DUNEA), Demetra Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), Demetra Kallitsi (ISOTECH)
Responsible author	Iva Pozniak ipozniak@dunea.hr Regional agency DUNEA
Deliverable description	<i>Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan (CDSEP) will be developed to ensure the project maximises its outreach to and impact on wider society and targeted audiences. Specific KPIs will be developed and regularly monitored (every 6 months) to ensure the CDSEP's effectiveness. The CDSEP will be continuously monitored and updated when relevant. (<=T6.1)</i>

¹ R = Document, report, DEM = Demonstrator, OTHER = Software, technical diagram, etc., DMP = Data Management Plan

² PU = Public, C-UE/EU-C = EU Confidential under Decision 2015/444, SEN = Sensitive

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Document history

Name	Date	Version	Description
Iva Pozniak	20/03/2023	V1	First draft
Demetra Orthodoxou, Demetra Kallitsi	30/03/2023	V1.1	First draft with comments
Iva Pozniak	26/04/2023	V1.2	Second draft
Demetra Orthodoxou, Demetra Kallitsi	03/05/2023	V1.2	Second draft with comments
Iva Pozniak	24/05/2023	V1.3	Third draft
Demetra Orthodoxou, Demetra Kallitsi	29/05/2023	V1.3	Third draft with comments
Iva Pozniak	29/05/2023	V1.4	Forth draft – ready for consortium comments
Iva Pozniak	26/06/2023	V1.5	Final document

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Disclaimer of warranties

This document has been prepared by SeaClear2.0 project partners as an account of work carried out within the framework of Grant Agreement no. 101093822. Neither the Project Coordinator, nor any signatory party of the SeaClear2.0 Project Consortium Agreement, nor any person acting on behalf of any of them:

- makes any warranty or representation whatsoever, express, or implied, with respect to the use of any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document, including merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose, that such use does not infringe on or interfere with privately owned rights, including any party's intellectual property; or
- makes any warranty or representation whatsoever, express, or implied, that this document is suitable to any particular user's circumstance; or
- assumes responsibility for any damages or other liability whatsoever (including any consequential damages, even if the Project Coordinator or any representative of a signatory party of the Project Consortium Agreement, has been advised of the possibility of such damages) resulting from your selection or use of this document or any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document.

SeaClear2.0 is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101093822). Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	7
1.1 Overall objective	7
1.2 Deliverable structure.....	8
1.3 Deliverable locations.....	8
2. Stakeholder engagement strategy	10
2.1 Community building – stakeholder mapping and identification process	10
2.2 Stakeholder mobilization	17
2.2.1 Communities of practice concept	17
2.2.2 SeaClear 2.0 CoPs	17
2.2.3 Stakeholders from collaborating projects.....	20
3. Communication and dissemination strategy	21
3.1 Communication and dissemination types.....	21
3.2 Communication and dissemination channels and tools	23
3.2.1 Targeted stakeholder communication and dissemination plan.....	28
4. Implementation plan.....	36
4.1 Communication plan.....	36
4.2 Dissemination plan.....	36
4.2.1 Dissemination for academic community.....	36
4.2.2 Dissemination for professional community	37
4.2.3 Dissemination for policy community	37
4.2.4 Communication and Dissemination for general public community	38
4.2.5 Dissemination for associated regions community	38
4.3 Communication and Dissemination timeline	39
5. Summary	48
6. References	49

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Definitions

- **Beneficiary:** A legal entity that is signatory of the EC Grant Agreement no. 101093822.
- **Consortium:** The SeaClear2.0 Consortium, comprising the list of beneficiaries below.
- **Consortium Agreement:** Agreement concluded amongst the SeaClear2.0 beneficiaries for the implementation of the Grant Agreement.
- **Grant Agreement:** The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the EC for the undertaking of the SeaClear2.0 project (Grant Agreement no. 101093822).

Beneficiaries of the SeaClear2.0 Consortium are referred to herein according to the following abbreviations:

- **TU Delft:** TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
- **DUNEA:** REGIONALNA AGENCIJA DUNEA
- **Fraunhofer:** FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV
- **HPA:** HAMBURG PORT AUTHORITY
- **ISOTECH:** ISOTECH LTD
- **MDanchor:** M. DANCHOR LTD
- **Subsea Tech:** SUBSEA TECH SAS
- **TECNOSUB:** TÉCNICAS Y OBRAS SUBACUÁTICAS, SLU
- **TUM:** TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN
- **UNIDU:** SVEUCILISTE U DUBROVNIKU
- **UTC:** UNIVERSITATEA TEHNICA CLUJ-NAPOCA
- **VEO:** VEOLIA PROPRETE
- **VLPF:** VENICE LAGOON PLASTIC FREE

Abbreviations

- **EC:** European Commission
- **GA:** Grant Agreement
- **WP:** Work Package
- **CDSEP:** Communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement strategy and plan
- **CoP:** Community of Practice
- **KPI:** Key Performance Indicator

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Executive summary

D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan aims to transfer project results to key target audiences in a timely, effective, and well-managed fashion using tailored Communication, Dissemination, Stakeholder Engagement tools. Dissemination is about sharing results, to stimulate their usage in further research or commercial development while communication is about how the results are shared. Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy are planned to gradually move from general communication in the beginning of the project to targeted dissemination, knowledge transfer and stakeholder engagement as the project progresses in years 2 and 3, culminating in communication and dissemination supporting the project exploitation activities in year 4.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

1. Introduction

1.1 Overall objective

Robotics and citizen engagement can play a crucial role in achieving the EU Mission for ocean, seas, and water health restoration by 2030. In this context, the EU-funded SeaClear2.0 project will develop an integrated approach to address the entire cycle of marine litter. The project focuses on reducing marine litter pollution, specifically from marine litter, in the Mediterranean. This will be achieved by using teams of autonomous, intelligent robots to monitor and collect marine seafloor and surface litter, and through participatory practices to identify site-specific measures for marine litter prevention and reduction. By identifying ways to valorise litter and extend policy-making, SeaClear2.0 will provide innovative solutions for effective marine litter management, further promoting the health of oceans, seas, and water bodies.

The present deliverable, D6.1 – Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan, is developed within the framework of Task T6.1 Development of Communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement strategy. The concept idea of Communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement strategy and plan (CDSEP) is to be formatted at the beginning of the project and continuously monitored and updated to ensure the project maximizes its outreach and impact. CDSEP activities are a core part of the project.

The main objective of this document is strategically designed communication and dissemination activities, rather than an ad hoc set of actions, in order to have the widest possible outreach and successful awareness-raising activities. In this way, the suitably framed communication and dissemination strategy, tools, and messages, will help to increase the success rate of our project, draw the attention of national governments, regional authorities, and other public and private funding sources to the need for and ultimate benefits of our research, attract the interest of potential users, encourage talented students and scientists to join our partner institutes and enterprises, enhance the reputation and visibility of the project and EU funding itself, at the local, national and international level, help the search for financial backers, licensees or industrial implementers to exploit our results, and finally generate market demand for the products or services developed.

The basis for the development of coherent CDSEP consists of previously formatted deliverables from project SeaClear which is the predecessor of the SeaClear 2.0 project. In such a manner, we are making sure to follow up on existing good practices, concepts, and tools while replicating and evolving the ideas for the new action. The SeaClear deliverables consulted are D7.1 “Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy”, deliverable presenting the dissemination and exploitation component of the project, detailing objectives, strategy, and planning, together with activities organized, and D7.3 “Creation and management of stakeholder community” as a detailed overview of the methodology used for stakeholder creation and management in order to attract critical mass around the project with a goal to achieve a significant number of users/potential early adopters of the SeaClear system, aggregated and involved in the validation and dissemination activities.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

1.2 Deliverable structure

This deliverable is structured to primarily identify the stakeholders, means of the stakeholder engagement, followed with types, channels, and tools of the communication and dissemination activities. CDSEP is making sure to evolve the project around the real people needs and interests, with the most suitable actions for each group. The tangible part of this deliverable is a realistic plan with a completion timeframe, along with monitoring tools in the form of specific KPIs, that will regularly be verified (every 6 months) to ensure the CDSEP's effectiveness. CDSEP is described through 6 main chapters: introduction part, stakeholder strategy, communication and dissemination strategy, communication and dissemination plan, and deliverable summary.

1.3 Deliverable locations

Plan for our communication and dissemination activities is to be decentralised, taking into account the specifics of each of the locations that we work in. Project area covers diverse European locations and is divided in 3 groups: project demonstration sites, project pilot sites and the associated regions area (Figure 1).

Project demonstrations sites are:

- **Marseille**
- **Dubrovnik Neretva county**
- **Tarragona**

Project pilot sites are:

- **Venice**
- **Ashdod**
- **Hamburg**

Figure 1: Coastal plastic pollution hotspots in the Mediterranean [EEA12]. Green = SeaClear2.0 demo sites; blue = SeaClear 2.0 pilot sites; red = all the other hotspots, where our results can be applied.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

At each demo site (see Figure 2), we will define and address specific environmental problems (connecting with the specific habitat and/or species of the area), covering the widest possible stakeholder profile. Our *Marseille demo* covers tourism and ports. The *Dubrovnik Neretva county demo* covers areas with aquaculture and fishing industry, but also protected areas and tourism with Mali Ston bay that is responsible for around 85% of total Mediterranean production of the European flat oyster. The area was declared a Special Natural Reserve in 1983 and is a part of the Natura 2000 ecological network. *Tarragona demo* site is a port city and a tourist attraction of the first order. The city houses the largest chemical hub in southern Europe. The Port of Tarragona plays a key role in the competitiveness of this hub.

Figure 2: SeaClear2.0 demonstration sites (Marseille port, Dubrovnik with Mali Ston bay, Tarragona port)

The insights from the demo locations will be backed up by pilot sites (see Figure 3) focusing on testing specific aspects or technologies, in the World Heritage Site of *Venice* and its Lagoon (Italy), with particular focus on the surrounding mass tourism seaside resort locations (tourism), *Ashdod* (Israel) and *Hamburg* (Germany) (ports, urban channels). Besides the demos and pilot sites, the project will include 5 associated regions, that will be defined later during the project. Concepts developed for project demos and pilots will be replicated in the associated region areas, thus widening the initial audience.

Figure 3: SeaClear2.0 pilot sites (Venice lagoon, Ashdod port, Hamburg port)

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

2. Stakeholder engagement strategy

2.1 Community building – stakeholder mapping and identification process

Stakeholders are defined as people who have an interest in a particular topic, either as individuals or representatives of an institution. This includes people who can influence decisions, as well as those who become affected by the decisions [1]. In order to achieve the widest possible dissemination, stakeholder mapping and identification is done by answering questions on who is affected by the project and who has an interest that can influence outcomes. Stakeholder mapping and identification is the first step in community building [2]. Community building is dedicated to attracting critical mass around the project. Apart from the users involved as partners in the project, a significant number of users/potential early adopters of the SeaClear and SeaClear 2.0 systems will be aggregated and involved in the dissemination activities. The aim is to consequently gather additional relevant stakeholders and individuals in the project areas. It is of the topmost importance to promote the project and its results beyond the project's own community, reach out to society, to communicate project research in a way that is understood by non-specialists, e.g., the media and the public, while also ensuring that research outputs are adequately disseminated to academia, industry, and policy-makers.

The process of stakeholder identification and engagement needs to be as inclusive as possible and ensure that as wide an experience as possible informs the research. In this sense *“an inclusive society is a society that over-rides differences of race, gender, class, generation, and geography and ensures inclusion, equality of opportunity as well as capability of all members of the society to determine an agreed set of social institutions that govern social interaction”* (UN, 2009). To create and sustain inclusive societies, it is crucial that all members of society are able and motivated to participate in civic, social, economic, and political activities, at the local, regional, and national levels.

The SeaClear2.0 partners’ consortium consists of 13 partners, comprising of 4 university institutions, 4 SMEs, a regional development agency, a port authority, one industry SME and one research organization, and one NGO. Due to this diversity among partners, SeaClear 2.0 has an interdisciplinary approach targeting and defining the project community groups.

There can be identified 5 main stakeholder groups:

- **Academic community**
- **Professional community**
- **Policy community**
- **General public community**
- **Associated regions community**

Each group has a variety of subgroups that we identified as important for our research, community activation, citizen empowerment, and participatory practices for identifying site-specific measures for marine litter prevention and reduction.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

The academic community is tackled mainly through journal publications, conferences, educational activities, and workshops. The community building type planned to be used for these types of stakeholders is primarily academic communication. The members will also disseminate the project results at international conferences in robotics, control, and marine technology. SeaClear 2.0 will organize workshops on a regular basis which will stimulate scientific discussions among the participants and transfer of information and ideas and can contribute to creating a common understanding of the project and its outcomes. During the workshops, in addition to reaching the external audience of the event, each research group aims for awareness and transparency of knowledge towards the various partners and its access by the other partners of the consortium.

Professional community, including partners consortium with its internal communication and knowledge exchange, includes also innovation and industry fairs, community connected through other projects with similar topics, and of course, project advisory board. The professional community from the industry sector is an important group being the potential applicant of the system. The project Advisory board falls also under this community, and it consists of external experts/stakeholders who provide expert opinions, knowledge, and stakeholder evaluations on the project progress, and advise on scientific and technical questions identified during project progress. The board is a multidisciplinary panel, consisting of both scientific and technical experts. An important part of the professional community is stakeholders from collaborating projects with a similar topic. Project collaboration brings together the widest possible community of professional stakeholders who are able to share their knowledge and best practices.

The policy community includes government agencies, pressure groups, media people, and individuals, including academics, who, for various reasons, have an interest in a particular policy field and attempt to influence it. A decision-maker community is responsible for making strategically important decisions which are of course based on a number of variables, including time constraints, resources available, and the amount and type of information available. SeaClear 2.0 policy communication and dissemination will make sure that the decision-makers have all the needed information, scientifically supported, to pass our results through their legislation and even apply it in practice, through the formation of the relevant regional/local documents.

The general public community is a big part of our stakeholder community and is the basic target group for project awareness-raising activities. The project affects, directly and indirectly, the general public, both in terms of impact on their daily life (waste problem and waste production), but also via the long-term goal of environmental preservation. Through all the activities that involve the general public, SeaClear 2.0 aims at informing and educating people about the topic of ocean preservation and marine litter problem, with the intention of influencing their attitudes, behaviours, and beliefs towards the achievement of meeting the objectives of the Mission to restore, protect and preserve the health of our oceans, seas, and waters by 2030.

Associated regions community are a specific part of the SeaClear 2.0 community identified with a specific approach to be tackled by the project communication and dissemination activities. To support the accelerated uptake of our solutions, SeaClear 2.0 will proactively target associated regions to enable them to closely follow the project and its demonstrations. Relevant deliverables and best practices will be shared with the associated regions, and they will also be invited to travel to demonstration events.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

SeaClear 2.0 will follow up the work of stakeholder mobilization done in SeaClear and widen the structure and actions. The stakeholder analysis matrix is a useful tool to help identify the key stakeholders who have the potential to influence or be influenced by the project activities and results. This classifies stakeholders in relation to the power that they hold in order to impact the project and their level of interest in the project, which the project manager needs to observe for stakeholder grouping [3]. When we mention the power to impact the project, it is in this case the level of influence to facilitate or block, and/or likely to impact it in positive or negative way, considering the timing or contexts in which the stakeholders have more or less influence over the outcomes of the project, and of course, the types of benefit they might derive from it. Based on the stakeholder matrix approach described by Robert Newcombe (1999), SeaClear 2.0 partners will involve the stakeholders identified in the table below (Table 1). The categories of the stakeholders listed below are not exhaustive.

LEVEL OF INTEREST			
		<i>Low</i>	<i>High</i>
POWER	<i>Low</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Tourists – Tour operators – Hospitality industry – Nautical industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Environmental NGOs – Technology industry – Fishery industry – Aquaculture industry – Local and regional community –
	<i>High</i>	- n/a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – University and Research Centres – Regional authority – Local authority – Waste management authority – Nature and environment protection public institutions – Port authorities – Media –

Table 1: SeaClear 2.0 stakeholder matrix

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

For each main stakeholder group, a subgroup has been identified, with estimations for outreach, as an overview of the people that will be circulating around the project. Details are in Table 2.

#	MAIN STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SHORT DESCRIPTION	SUBGROUP	ESTIMATED OUTREACH (APPROX. NO.)
1	ACADEMIC COMMUNITY	<i>Academic organizations (public or private) with their scientists and students in the relevant field - underwater and aerial robotics, sensors, artificial intelligence and classification to automatic control, system integrators, environmental science, marine biology, and ecology, integrated coastal zone management, waste management, port management.</i>	Universities (4 from project consortium + 1 from each demo/pilot=6)	10
			Research organizations (1 from project consortium + 1 from each demo/pilot=6)	7
			Educational centres	3
			Scientists/researchers	50
			University students	50
			Primary and secondary students	300
2	PROFESSIONAL COMMUNITY	<i>Professional organizations and individuals, with special focus on industry sector (public or private) in the relevant field (underwater and aerial robotics, sensors, artificial intelligence and classification to automatic control, system integrators, environmental science, marine biology, and ecology, fisheries, aquaculture, integrated coastal zone management, waste management, port management, tourism/hospitality)</i>	Major corporations (1 per each demo/pilot)	6
			Relevant SMEs – connected to the project topic (2 per each demo/pilot)	12
			Relevant NGOs – connected to the project topic (2 per each demo/pilot)	12
			Divers (7 per each demo/pilot)	42
			CoP members (min. 15 per each CoP)	90
3	POLICY COMMUNITY	<i>Local and regional government units and decision-makers in the administrative scope of each project demo/pilot site.</i>	Local government units (2 per each demo/pilot)	12
			Local decision makers (mayors - 1 per each demo/pilot)	6
			Regional decision makers (1 per each demo/pilot)	6

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

4	GENERAL PUBLIC	<p><i>General public community from the project area (demo and pilot sites), reached through the project's communication and dissemination activities – our estimations are to reach approx. 30% of the people living in the area.</i></p>	<p>Marseille with 876 602¹ inhabitants, Dubrovnik Neretva County 122 571², Tarragona 830 075³, Venice 258 685⁴, Hamburg 1 906 411⁵, Ashdod 225 974⁶ = total 4 220 318 inhabitants on project demo/pilot sites, 30% = approx. 1,2 million</p>	1,2 million
5	ASSOCIATED REGIONS COMMUNITY	<p><i>Associated regions community that will be tackled with the project's implementation but also with replicatory activities at the associated regions areas. These numbers are only estimations, since these regions are yet to be defined, altogether 5 associated regions with approx. 200 000 inhabitants each area, taking 30% of the people living in the area, i.e., 60 000 people x 5 = 300 000 people outreach.</i></p>		300 000

Table 2: SeaClear 2.0 stakeholder groups estimations

¹ <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/6676182?geo=COM-13055#consulter>

² https://podaci.dzs.hr/media/pchp4exb/7-1-3_procjena-stanovnistva-rh-u-2020.pdf

³ <https://www.ine.es/>

⁴ <https://demo.istat.it/>

⁵ https://www.statistik-nord.de/fileadmin/Dokumente/Statistische_Berichte/bevoelkerung/A_I_S_1_j_H/A_I_S1_j21.pdf

⁶ <https://www.cbs.gov.il/en/settlements/Pages/default.aspx?mode=Yeshuv>

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

In the process of stakeholder engagement, a stakeholder impact assessment has been made (Table 3), as an overview of community influence in correlation to project goals and Mission Ocean outcomes. This table follows the structure presented in Table 1, that was formatted in the procedure of stakeholder mapping and identification.

Project impact goal	Relevant Mission Ocean outcomes and objectives	Relevant stakeholder groups	Reasons for being interested in the project	Activities to engage this target group	Risks to activities	Risks to impact	Who is responsible and what resources are needed?	Timing
Community activation, citizen empowerment, and participatory practices for identifying site-specific measures for marine litter prevention and reduction, thus supporting the implementation of the WFD and MSFD	Promote EU-Wide annual Ocean literacy campaigns in cooperation with EU4Ocean (by 2030)	ACADEMIC COMMUNITY	<i>Achieving impact from research and collaboration opportunities.</i>	<i>Stakeholder engagement will be implemented through mobilization construct of Communities of practice CoP (see chapter 2.2)</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Weak attendance and interest in the project. – main mitigation are project communication and dissemination activities prepared in such manner to tackle each relevant stakeholder group.</i> <i>Poor coordination from CoP coordinators. – main mitigation action is smart choice of CoP coordinators that will coordinate the stakeholders in their home area accordingly.</i> <i>Sudden risks (such is corona pandemic and similar outbursts that we cannot control) – main mitigation</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Limited online reach – mitigation measure to this risk is firstly the smartly constructed CDSEP document in order to achieve the widest possible online outreach.</i> <i>No new materials developed – project will continuously develop new materials in the form of public project deliverables that will be useful insight instruments in the project concepts.</i> <i>Poor engagement possibilities – mitigation measure for this risk is the construct of CoP communities with CoP coordinators.</i> 	<i>WP6 coordinator ISOTECH with DUNEA support and relevant CoP coordinators, under strong support from Lead partner TU Delft. The foreseen resources dedicated to all WP6 activities are €883.316,00 financed from SeaClear 2.0 general budget.</i>	<i>See chapter 4. For detailed Communication and dissemination plan.</i>
		PROFESSIONAL COMMUNITY	<i>Opportunities to invest, connect to professionals from the same or similar sector, opportunities for business expansion.</i>					
		POLICY COMMUNITY	<i>Using research to influence through policy</i>					
		GENERAL PUBLIC	<i>Educational and inspirational opportunities leading to increase of the quality of life in general.</i>					

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

		ASSOCIATED REGIONS COMMUNITY			<i>measure is assurance of good online communication and connection that can assure the continuous of the project implementation, and give options for online participation and mobilization of stakeholders.</i>			
--	--	------------------------------	--	--	---	--	--	--

Table 3: SeaClear 2.0 stakeholder impact planning

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

2.2 Stakeholder mobilization

2.2.1 Communities of practice concept

One of the concepts used for the mobilization of stakeholders through the SeaClear 2.0 project, follows the concept used in SeaClear project and will continue the effort to successfully mobilize the stakeholders around a similar scheme. The methodology used is based on the idea of a Community of Practice (CoP). This well-practiced method has become known through the research and publications of Lave and Wenger (1991), Wenger (1998), and Wenger-Trayner (2010, 2014) [4]. It is defined as a voluntary group of people who, sharing a common concern or a passion, come together to explore joint ideas, repertoire of resources, experiences, and stories. The concept has displayed a very useful perspective on learning, considering human nature – the need to collaborate, interact and exchange knowledge with a group of people with similar mindsets [5]. In the case of the SeaClear and SeaClear 2.0 communities, the passion connecting the stakeholders is marine environment protection and joint effort to solve the marine litter problem.

The CoP concept is significantly different from the usual groups inside which people interact since it gives structure to meet mutual needs, but not in an informal way, as is usually done for example in a general network social group. It also notably differs from formal work-oriented groups where the motives to collaborate are formed by the workplace itself. CoP gives an official frame for people, supportive to act on their individual ideas and passions with collective contribution, without exact work-scope restrictions [6].

The focal construct of CoP work is a participatory process, which aims at bringing together relevant stakeholders or those who have an interest in each issue or decision, into contact with one another to let them collaborate, discuss and at the very end take a decision. The key objective of this process is to enhance levels of trust between the different actors, to share information and institutional knowledge, project goals and results, and to generate relevant good practices. The process takes the view that all stakeholders have relevant experience, knowledge, and information that ultimately will inform and improve the quality of the decision-making process as well as any actions that may result. With sufficient time, resources, and preparation, this process can be a very effective tool for bringing diverse constituencies together to build consensus around complex, multifaceted, and in some cases, divisive issues.

2.2.2 SeaClear 2.0 CoPs

To ensure continuous stakeholder engagement, in SeaClear we formatted Communities of Practice (CoPs) facilitated by the end-users DUNEA and HPA. CoPs had several meeting opportunities proposed by the end-user, and they took different forms (workshops, round tables, working groups, clean-up actions, etc.) and covered several aspects. The role of end-user DUNEA and HPA was to provide inputs for discussion. This approach allowed for highlighting the direct impact that marine litter has on tourism and industry, and especially the way it could be processed in decision-making legislations of the areas, with an overview of the benefits or drawbacks that certain waste behaviours and policies can generate. This triggered the sense of belonging of the stakeholders and their willingness to be part of the process and resulted in a new concept of participatory and science-based decision-making and planning for waste management, risk prevention, and marine pollution problematics.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

CoP community is intended as a living body that can change its members and continuously evolve depending on the topic, and in this case, the specific project phase. Members are free to join or leave the network without any strict obligations. SeaClear created a stakeholder database where the stakeholder's name, institutional name, and contact were mentioned, thus entering a wider web of contacts with collaborating projects. This was especially important for the Dubrovnik Neretva area, while Hamburg Port had a specific approach, mostly to the wide community of the Port itself, where a database was not necessary. The same stakeholder database will continue the work through SeaClear 2.0 with the addition of other project locations.

The existing CoPs gather a total of 49 members, most of them belonging to the public sector (84%) and a minority of members belonging to the private sector (16%). Altogether 29 stakeholder institutions are involved, 13 institutions for Dubrovnik Neretva CoP and 16 institutions from Hamburg Port CoP. Considering the sectoral structure of the SeaClear general CoP, the majority of the community belongs to the sector of environment, covering 29%, followed by the port authority sector covering 21%, then 16% belonging to the higher education sector, and 16% belonging to entrepreneurship.

SeaClear 2.0 will widen the existing two project CoPs with four more CoP groups formatted in project demo/pilot locations, and five more CoPs in the associated regions area. With this, we will reach the number of 11 CoPs. Details as in the table below (Table 4).

COP NAME	LOCATION TYPE	ADMINISTRATIVE AREA + LOCATION SPECIFICS	COORDINATOR	MINIMUM NO. OF MEMBERS	SHORT DESCRIPTION
CoP for marine litter problem in Dubrovnik Neretva County	DEMO	Dubrovnik Neretva County – 22 local government units (5 cities and 7 municipalities), 60% of the area under NATURA 2000 protection and 80% of the surface = marine surface area. Nature protected sites, touristic areas, and specific shellfish industry area Mali Ston Bay.	DUNEA	15	<i>A group of people acting on a regional level, created in collaboration with another EU project called MARLESS.</i>
CoP for tourism and ports in Marseille	DEMO	Marseille harbour, at Arenck dock and Corbières beach - litter is drained down to the dock during storms. 480 kg of litter collected at Corbières beach clean-up in 2021 (including heavier litter).	SST	15	<i>CoP Regional and national NGOs involved in marine litter collection, public institutions (Region SUD, City of Marseilles, Marseilles harbor).</i>

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Tarragona Port City CoP	DEMO	Tarragona Port – combines maritime traffic/port operations, tourism, fishing, and industrial activities = large amounts of marine litter	TECNOSUB	15	A group of persons/institutions involved either in professional or leisure activities in marine environment, including Tarragona Port Authority
Hamburg port CoP	PILOT	Hamburg Port - murky waters, urban / touristic / naval equipment / construction waste items	HPA	15	A group of experts from Hamburg port authority itself, to support the challenging procedures for demonstrations in the port area.
Venice Lagoon CoP	PILOT	Venice Lagoon World Heritage Site -several factors for plastics pollution including morphological setting; decreasing resident density and increasing transient population; and 10 rivers flowing into Venice Lagoon bringing in plastic litter	VLPF	15	A set of different environmental NGOs operating in the metropolitan city of Venice and its lagoon. We also set out synergic cooperation with other HORIZON projects: MAELSTROM, INNOPLASTIC, REMEDIES and the WWF international program Plastic Smart Cities from the local up to the Mediterranean scale of action. Finally, we include in our CoPs SMEs devoted to Blue Circular Economy.
Ashdod Area CoP	PILOT	Ashdod - heavily polluted. Growing port infrastructure and tourist attraction efforts expected to worsen the current situation.	MDAnchor	15	A group of people from Ashdod municipality, environment protection bodies, and DANCHOR to support planning and execution of the pilot at the port and surrounding area.
5 Associated region CoPs	ASSOCIATED REGIONS	TBC	TBC	10 per each CoP = 50	There will be formatted 5 additional CoPs, 1 for each associated region, and they will follow up the project guidelines for CoP activation and coordination.

Table 4: SeaClear 2.0 Communities of practice

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

The variety of the locations and thus the societal heterogeneity of the areas, give a wide spectrum of diversity to be taken into account when formatting the CoPs and the CoP actions themselves. It is of high importance to have CoP coordinators to be originating from the area, and to develop an intuitive approach for coordination of the relevant group, creating an enabling environment for accountability, and promoting participatory and inclusive processes. Each CoP will give inputs depending on the needs and habits of its members, thus enriching the project knowledge and results.

The exact procedure for enrolling as a member of each SeaClear 2.0 CoP, is simple and consists of filling in two documents: *an informational sheet and a stakeholder consent form*. By reading all relevant project data in the informational sheet and by signing the stakeholder consent form, a person becomes a CoP member. By participating as a stakeholder in the SeaClear 2.0 project, stakeholders will also become part of a wider network of CoPs from 11 European areas, and benefit from workshops and knowledge transfer between different sector participants, focusing on the same issues – marine litter problematics. They will also be able to enjoy information sharing on robotic topics, the marine environment, and tourism/waste management issues among people with similar mindsets. In order to respect the GDPR rules, stakeholders will be informed in the informational sheet that the personal data collected will only be used for the purpose of the SeaClear 2.0 project within the project consortium and the European Commission, and will not be disclosed to any external sources. Stakeholders will be able to request modification or removal of the data at any time with a short request to the CoP coordinator. All data will be used in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union. CoP coordination meetings will be organized by each CoP coordinator, upon project activities dynamics, following the project milestones timeframe.

2.2.3 Stakeholders from collaborating projects

Besides the CoP members, the stakeholders from collaborating projects are identified as a very important stakeholder group. The collaborations achieved in SeaClear will be continued in SeaClear 2.0.

Through SeaClear 2.0, it is of utmost importance to act in connection with other Mission Ocean projects, exploring synergies, while also guaranteeing an overall “branding” of the mission with coordinated visuals to be used. By strengthening the collaboration with similar projects under the Mission Ocean “flag,” SeaClear 2.0 will help achieve the 2030 target of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”, protecting, and restoring the health of our ocean and waters through research and innovation, citizen engagement and blue investments. The estimated KPI for building links with other Missions, Projects, and Initiatives is a minimum of 3.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

3. Communication and dissemination strategy

3.1 Communication and dissemination types

Communication is the process of exchanging information. Dissemination is the action of spreading information to the relevant community. Communication in HORIZON EUROPE means promoting the action and the results, while dissemination means making the project results public for other to use.

Communication covers the whole project (including results), starts at the outset of the project, covers multiple audiences, beyond the project's own community, informing and engaging with society, to show how it can benefit from research including the media and general public. Dissemination covers project results only and happens once results are available, aiming at specialist audiences, i.e., groups that may use the results in their own work, including peer groups, industry, professional organizations, and policymakers, enabling the take-up and use of results. [7]

The CDSEP activities are planned to gradually move from general communication at the beginning of the project to targeted dissemination, knowledge transfer, and stakeholder engagement as the project progresses in years 2 and 3, culminating in communication and dissemination supporting the project exploitation activities in year 4. Dissemination is about sharing the project results with key target audiences, each of which requires specific means and channels. Dissemination activities will begin towards the end of year 1 of the project and will run till the end.

Through the communication and dissemination activities, we will clearly aim to demonstrate the ways in which research and innovation are contributing to a European 'Innovation Union' and account for public spending by providing tangible proof that collaborative research adds value by:

- showing how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible, notably in achieving scientific excellence, contributing to competitiveness, and solving societal challenges;
- showing how the outcomes are relevant to our everyday lives, by creating jobs, introducing novel technologies, or making our lives more comfortable in other ways;
- making better use of the results, by making sure they are taken up by decision-makers to influence policy-making and by industry and the scientific community to ensure follow-up.

SeaClear 2.0 divided communication and dissemination types by target groups, positioning in that way people in the focus of our action. Through these 4 types of communication and dissemination, the project ensures impact on four main levels: scientific, economic, policy, and societal. The main communication and dissemination types identified are:

- ***Academic communication and dissemination;***
- ***Professional communication and dissemination;***
- ***Policy communication and dissemination;***
- ***General public communication and dissemination.***

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Academic communication and dissemination are a highly structured way of effective and formal presentation of project goals and ideas within a scholastic environment, targeting the academic community and covering the scientific level. Academic dissemination provides the opportunity to showcase the project results to others familiar with the relevant scientific field. The academic community will be tackled mainly through journal publications, conferences, educational activities, and workshops.

Professional communication and dissemination are a specifically structured way of reaching out to the experts in the relevant sector, i.e., the professional community. This type of communication includes internal communication and knowledge exchange between the partner consortium and project advisory board but specifically focuses on external communication and dissemination through innovation and industry fairs, industry events at project demo and pilot sites, and connections and synergies with other projects working on similar topics. It covers the economic level of impact. The professional community, including industry, presents a potential applicant of the system and benefits from the transfer of knowledge between academia and industry. An important part of the professional community is stakeholders from collaborating projects with a similar topic. Project collaborations bring together the wider possible community of professional stakeholders who are able to share their knowledge and best practices.

Policy communication and dissemination is a specific type of communication/dissemination directed at the decision-makers and policymakers. This communication and dissemination type ensures the information disperses and appeals to the decision-makers/policymakers. In order to facilitate tailor-made design specifically for policy communication materials, specific target groups of policymakers will be identified. Scientific facts and conclusions are the main instruments that should produce the desired change in policy and legislation framework. The aim is to use research to influence policy.

Public communication and dissemination refer to the act of dispersing information to the widest possible community through the use of various tools or methods, impacting the societal level. The public as a general community, encompasses various subsets of stakeholders concerned with diverse issues. General public communication and dissemination are extremely important for awareness raising on the huge threat and problem that marine litter poses for the environment and people in general. This environmental problem cannot be limited to only specific community groups, since it affects people and the planet as a whole, without the administrative and cultural borders. By tackling the general public community, the project aims to invoke each individual to think about the selection of products they use in everyday life. The idea is to raise awareness of the collective responsibility and role of each individual who can try to reduce the carbon footprint and the amount of waste on this planet and thus be an example to children and future generations.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

3.2 Communication and dissemination channels and tools

SeaClear 2.0 communication and dissemination strategy identified two main communication and dissemination channels in which specific communication and dissemination tools are grouped together, as follows:

- **digital mode channel** (web page, social media, newsletter, publications, etc.),
- **live mode channel** (project various events)

In this phase of the project, we have identified altogether 20 various tools that tackle all main target groups. In the table below we formatted an overview of the tools (Table 5) with listed key performance indicators (KPIs) for each tool. These are primary foreseen numbers structured as a monitoring outline. The data is indicative at this stage of the project implementation and will change according to the project dynamics. This document is structured as a live document that will adapt to real situations and be revised accordingly, in order to achieve the project's main goals.

CHANNEL	TOOL	SHORT DESCRIPTION	COMMUNICATION / DISSEMINATION TYPE COVERED	KPI
DIGITAL	website	<i>Central channel of dissemination for the project news and updates, and for any public project outputs and deliverables.</i>	Academic, Professional, General	1
	social media	<i>Virtual communities and networks of interactive media technologies that facilitate the sharing of information, ideas, interests, and other forms of expression. SeaClear 2.0 uses Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube.</i>	Academic, Professional, General	5
	video	<i>SeaClear 2.0 plans to develop an explanatory animation video at the beginning of the project as a visual description of the project's aim and foreseen results. One video will also be developed following each successful system verification event, which will be disseminated further on the project's YouTube channel and social media channels. The expected number of videos produced is 7 (1 at the project beginning, 1 for each demo/pilot site =6).</i>	Academic, Professional, General	7
	press release	<i>Press release is defined as a statement/information delivered to members of the media. This tool includes press releases published generally on behalf of the project (in English). It is expected to have 7 main press releases on behalf the project in general, upon project start and following each project system verification event (1 at the project beginning, 1 for each demo/pilot site =6).</i>	Academic, Professional, General	7

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

	institutional website post	<i>Project news posts by each project partner on their institutional website, in their own languages, and in their own dynamics. We foresee for each partner to have a minimum of 4 individual news posts on their institutional websites.</i>	Academic, Professional, General	52
	scientific publications	<i>Preparing and issuing a scientific article to be published in a peer reviewed journal.</i>	Academic	52+
	newsletter	<i>Newsletter is an electronic report containing project news distributed digitally to people subscribed. An average of 1 newsletter per year is planned.</i>	Academic, Professional, General	4
	geographical storytelling tool	<i>This citizen-science tool will engage snorkelers, divers, fishers, and others to report sightings of floating and seabed marine litter, creating an openly available map of litter hotspots.</i>	Academic, Professional, General	1
	mobile application	<i>This mobile app will use gamification to engage users in beach clean-up activities.</i>	Academic, Professional, General	1
	LIVE	project meetings	<i>Formal project meetings organized every 6 months in order to facilitate successful project implementation.</i>	Academic, Professional
system verification events		<i>Formal project events for a complete system or specific system parts verification processes at project demo locations and pilot locations.</i>	Academic, Professional	6
industry events		<i>Industry event is envisioned as an event targeting industry end-users, that follows the official project system verification events.</i>	Academic, Professional	6

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

participatory decision-making workshops	<i>Key stakeholders, including decision and policy-makers, at each pilot/demo site will be invited to participate in a decision-making workshop, where through participatory practices they will identify site-specific marine litter prevention and reduction solutions. A brief educational event where a group of people engages in intensive discussion on a particular subject, in this case, marine litter. The idea is to have a minimum of 1 workshop per demo/pilot site, with a minimum of 15 stakeholders.</i>	Academic, Professional	6
policy round table	<i>Knowledge transfer activity with policy end-users where barriers and opportunities for the prevention and minimization of marine litter and for the development and deployment of the project's innovation will be discussed, through an analysis of the relevant policies. Policy recommendations from the policy review and policy roundtable will be included in a Policy White Paper. This event should gather minimum of 30 participants.</i>	Policy	1
international collaborative workshop	<i>International workshop organised in collaboration with lighthouse twin projects MAELSTROM and InnoPlastic, with minimum 50 participants.</i>	Academic, Professional, General	1
3-day scientific workshop	<i>Organization of a 3-day scientific workshop with 30 participants in the last year of the project.</i>	Academic, Professional	1
beach clean-ups	<i>Beach clean-up events to remove litter items from the local environment, but more importantly to have a direct impact on the local community participating in the event and raise awareness about the marine litter problem. It is planned to have 2 beach clean-ups per demo/pilot site.</i>	General	12
CoP activation events	<i>Event for CoP activation, where the CoP idea will be presented, described and where future members will get all the information on the benefits of being the CoP member, but also of the expectations of the membership.</i>	Academic, Professional, General	11

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

conferences	<i>Participation in conferences and congresses to disseminate the project's scientific knowledge to the research community. Planned is at least 2 per academic partner.</i>	Academic, Professional	8
various outreach events	<i>Other outreach events organized by partners, tailored for the specificities of their area, in order to raise awareness on marine litter problematics and to spread the SeaClear 2.0 main messages – it can be artistic events such as for example upcycled art exhibitions and photography exhibitions, sports events, educational activities, workshops and Project-led competitions for kids and students, radio/TV interviews, podcasts etc.</i>	General	6
outreach events at Associated Regions	<i>Each Associated Region will have to implement one public outreach event to raise awareness about the marine litter issue and the SeaClear2.0 project</i>	General	5
Calls for action	<i>These calls of actions will be launched through social media at each of the pilot/demo sites and will aim to incite citizen/tourist involvement.</i>	General	20

Table 5: Communication and dissemination main channels and tools

Besides the communication and dissemination channels and tools and the measurable KPIs, the Project has specific key performance indicators that we plan to achieve by implementing all described tangible digital and live tools, details in Table 6.

TARGET DESCRIPTION	KPI
<i>Policy White Paper: A document containing the outputs from the policy analysis and the policy roundtable.</i>	1
<i>Positive feedback of stakeholders during actions (in terms of empowerment to minimize marine litter)</i>	At least 85%
<i>Reduction of beach litter at the pilot/demo sites</i>	At most 20 items per 100m of coastline
<i>Stakeholder organizations to be included in participatory activities for building ocean literacy and in surface and seabed marine litter identification, collection, and monitoring</i>	At least 10
<i>Cooperation/connections/links with other Missions, Projects, and Initiatives</i>	At least 3
<i>The total number of people reached through the communication and dissemination activities of the project</i>	5 million

Table 6: Specific project KPIs to be achieved

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Apart from the identification of main communication and dissemination types, channels, and tools, with the aim of having the unified “backbone” vision throughout all project communication and dissemination activities, the SeaClear 2.0 project has formed a set of explicit communication messages that will be spread to the public. The goal of the formation of these messages is to have a deeper approach to specific audiences in relation to the project implementation plan. These messages can be used as slogans i.e., as memorable phrases used to advertise the project in the public space.

- ≈ **SeaClear2.0 PREVENT – REDUCE – REUSE:** *SeaClear 2.0 addresses the full life cycle of marine litter, by offering prevention, reduction, and repurposing solutions.*
- ≈ **OCEAN LITERACY FOR ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP:** *SeaClear 2.0 activates and empowers citizens by offering innovative, participatory knowledge transfer and ocean literacy opportunities.*
- ≈ **SMART ROBOTS FOR CLEAN OCEANS:** *SeaClear2.0 presents its fleet of AI-powered autonomous robots for detection, mapping, and collection of marine waste from the seabed and surface.*

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

3.2.1 Targeted stakeholder communication and dissemination plan

To have a general overview of communication/dissemination activities by each target group, we formatted all the details in Table 7, defining the Who, Why, What and How of the project’s communication and dissemination activities. The When (i.e., the timeline of the activities) is presented in the Gantt charts/dissemination timelines that follow (Tables 9 – 12).

COMMUNICATION / DISSEMINATION	WHO TO TELL? i.e., Target Group and Subgroup	WHY TELL THEM?	WHAT IS THE MESSAGE? i.e., key information that we want to share with the target audience.	HOW WILL THE MESSAGE BE DELIVERED? i.e., which Tools will be used to share the key messages
Communication	General Public: Adults	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise awareness about marine litter - Raise awareness about Mission Oceans - Raise awareness about European-funded research (i.e., what the taxpayer’s money is funded) and its importance - Link EU-funded research with important societal issues - Show the success of European collaboration - Share best practices - Promote project’s activities and results - Maximize the impacts of project results - Engage with key stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marine litter is a key environmental threat [info. about the main sources and impacts of marine litter, focusing on floating and seabed litter] - Seabed marine litter might be “out of sight” but has important environmental and economic impacts - The solution to the marine litter issue begins with personal actions - Sharing of best practices that can be implemented personally and collectively to address marine litter - What are the aims of Mission Oceans - What is the SeaClear2.0 project [link to three key comms messages] - How is artificial intelligence used in the SeaClear2.0 project to address marine litter - How SeaClear2.0 helps meet the Mission Oceans and the US Sustainable Development Goals - Information about the Geographical Information Storytelling Tool and encouragement to use it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social Media - Video (project animation video and project demo/pilot videos) - Press releases - Various outreach events (radio and TV interviews, podcasts, Project-led competitions) - CoP activation events at each demo & pilot site and at the Associated Regions - Calls for Action

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information about the marine litter app and encouragement to use it - Sharing information about the Communities of Practice and reasons for joining - Sharing information about community activation events, their purpose, and encouragement to join/participate - Information about project-initiated competitions targeting adults - Technological/scientific project results “translated” for adult general public 	
Communication	General Public: Children and youth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise awareness about marine litter - Raise awareness about Mission Oceans - Raise awareness about areas of technological innovation/work for the future - Raise awareness of the importance of EU-funded research - Share best practices - Promote project’s activities and results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marine litter is a key environmental threat [info. about the main sources and impacts of marine litter, focusing on floating and seabed litter] - Seabed marine litter might be “out of sight” but has important environmental and economic impacts - The solution to the marine litter issue begins with personal actions - Sharing of best practices/actions that children and youth could specifically take to minimize their contribution to marine litter - collectively to address marine litter - What are the aims of Mission Oceans - What is the SeaClear2.0 project [link to three key comms messages] - How is artificial intelligence used in the SeaClear2.0 project to address marine litter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video (project animation video and project demo/pilot videos) - Various outreach events (radio and TV interviews, podcasts, Project-led competitions) - CoP activation events at each demo & pilot site and at the Associated Regions - Calls for Action

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How SeaClear2.0 helps meet the Mission Oceans and the US Sustainable Development Goals - Sharing information about community activation events, their purpose, and encouragement to join/participate - Information about project-initiated competitions targeting children and youth - Technological/scientific project results “translated” for children and youth 	
Communication	Media/Journalists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote project’s activities and results - Raise citizen’s awareness of how their money is spent - Show the success of European collaboration - Share best practices with others - Maximize results’ impacts - Generate market demand for the products or services developed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The aims and goals of SeaClear2.0 - SeaClear2.0 works at the nexus of technology, civic activation, and policy to address the issue of marine litter - Information about community activation events and tools (e.g., app., geographical information storytelling tool), their purpose, and their results - Information about demos/pilots and invitation to participate - Highlights from project results and how they can help address the marine litter issue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project website - Press releases - Various outreach events (radio and TV interviews, podcasts) - Industry events at each demo/pilot site
Dissemination	Academic Community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Universities - Research organizations - Scientists/ Researchers - University students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attract the best experts for the SeaClear2.0 team - Promote project’s activities and results - Maximize results’ impacts - Allow other researchers to go a step forward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information about the research teams in SeaClear2.0 and their work - Information about the offerings of the SeaClear2.0 system, relevant to AI technology: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Aerial and underwater imagery o Sonar imagery o Broadband communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific publications - Conference presentations - Scientific repositories e.g., Zenodo - Project website (where public deliverables will be uploaded)

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribute to the advancement of the state of the art - Trigger new collaborations and opportunities - Make scientific results a common good 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information about the offerings of the SeaClear2.0 system, relevant to marine litter research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Robotic collection technology o Consistent, long-term, and large area marine litter monitoring o Mapping of marine litter presence and composition (objects from 15-20cm) o Real-time reporting of marine litter observations o Surface and seabed collection of heavy objects up to 250kg without direct crew intervention o Integration with European marine litter database - Information about the offerings of the SeaClear2.0 system, relevant to social sciences: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Methods and techniques for citizen activation for marine litter reduction o Participatory methods for site-specific decision-making on marine litter - Information about the R&I advancements of the project that can be publicly shared 	
Dissemination	Professional Community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SMEs and larger companies (potential project) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote project's activities and results - Generate market demand for the products or services developed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The aims and goals of SeaClear2.0 regarding technological innovation and its potential application 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industry events at demo & pilot sites and at Associated Regions - Industrial exhibitions/fairs - Professional social media i.e. LinkedIn

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

	product end-users)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Help to tackle a problem and respond to an existing demand - Trigger new collaborations and opportunities - Contribute to the advancement of the state of the art 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information about the industry partners in SeaClear2.0, their work, and their role in the project (motivation for participation) - Continuous information about the technological innovation progress in SeaClear2.0 - Highlights of demonstration/pilot tests with emphasis on the applicability of the SeaClear2.0 system for the needs of the various end-users (e.g., ports, touristic locations, etc.) - Information about specific technological/industry offerings of the SeaClear2.0 system: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Mapping of marine litter presence and composition (objects from 15-20cm) o Control and evolution of marine litter presence o Unmanned surface and seafloor litter collection and water sampling o Surface and seabed collection of heavy objects up to 250kg without direct crew intervention o Distribution, renting and training on robotic systems o Distribution of AI-based algorithms and sensors that can be added to other technologies o Use of web/phone app to manage obtained data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration/exchange with other relevant projects and consortia - Project website (where public deliverables will be uploaded)
--	--------------------	---	---	---

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Communication and dissemination	Professional Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage with stakeholders - Share best practices - Promote project's activities and results - Maximize results' impacts - Trigger new collaborations and opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marine litter is a key environmental threat - Information on the main sources and impacts of marine litter - Seabed marine litter might be "out of sight" but has important environmental and economic impacts - Sharing of best practices that can be implemented personally and collectively to address marine litter - SeaClear2.0 works at the nexus of technology, civic activation, and policy to address the issue of marine litter - What is artificial intelligence and how it is being used in the SeaClear2.0 project to address marine litter - Information about the Geographical Information Storytelling Tool and encouragement to use it - Information about the marine litter app and encouragement to use it - Sharing information about the Communities of Practice and reasons for joining - Sharing information about community activation events, their purpose, and encouragement to join/participate - Information about the offerings of the SeaClear2.0 system, relevant to marine litter research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Consistent, long-term, and large area marine litter monitoring o Real-time reporting of marine litter observations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CoP activation events at each demo & pilot site and at the Associated Regions - Social Media - Newsletters - Press releases - Project website - Various outreach events (radio and TV interviews, podcasts)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NGOs - Divers - CoP members 			

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Surface and seabed collection of heavy objects up to 250kg without direct crew intervention ○ Integration with European marine litter database - Information about the offerings of the SeaClear2.0 system, relevant to social sciences: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Methods and techniques for citizen activation for marine litter reduction ○ Participatory methods for site-specific decision-making on marine litter - “Translated” information about the R&I advancements of the project that can be publicly shared 	
Dissemination	Policy Community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local government - Regional government - National government - EU policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lead to new legislation or recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information about the SeaClear2.0 work as regards policy-relevant outputs - The importance of participatory methods in policy-making - Main results from the participatory workshops that will be implemented at each demo/pilot site (and possibly Associated Regions) and how they relate to policy-making for marine litter reduction - Results from the Policy Roundtable - Results from the evaluation of the project within the EU Taxonomy Regulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participatory decision-making workshops at each demo & pilot site (and where relevant Associated Regions) - Policy Roundtable - Policy White Paper - Participation in relevant policy events by other projects/ initiatives and EU/ CINEA - Project Website - Project Deliverables relating to policy

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Dissemination	Associated Regions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote project's activities and results - Harness interest in transferring and testing the SeaClear2.0 system (or parts of it) - Generate market demand for the products or services developed - Help to tackle a problem and respond to an existing demand - Trigger new collaborations and opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key information about the project's aims and technological innovation, including the SeaClear2.0 system's offerings (as described above) - Updates about SeaClear2.0's progress in all areas of work (technology, citizen activation, policy) - Messages about how the SeaClear2.0 can be used to address the needs of the various end-users (i.e., providing a solution to their pains) - Information about the upcoming replication at Associated Regions - Details about the call for Associated Regions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social Media - Project website - Newsletters - Press releases

Table 7: SeaClear 2.0 Communication/dissemination activities by target group

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

4. Implementation plan

4.1 Communication plan

Running throughout the duration of the project, communication is concerned with communicating about the project to the general public using popular communication channels and establishing a recognizable project identity/brand. Year 1 will focus on communicating within the consortium, to other relevant initiatives, and to the general public. The aim is to raise awareness to as wide an audience as possible, about the project and about the issue of marine litter. In years 2-4 communication activities will focus on information about project results, and target some of the project's specific target groups. The appropriate language will be used to share the scientific/technical outputs of the projects to these audiences. Press releases and news items will be developed, translated into project languages, and shared on social media and the project website, to disseminate important project milestones, breakthroughs, activities, and events. Short videos, fit for social media, will be developed to share key information on the project.

4.2 Dissemination plan

Dissemination is about sharing the project results with key target audiences, each of which requires specific means and channels. Dissemination activities will begin towards the end of year 1 of the project and will run till the end. The dissemination activities plan has been divided according to the targeting audience defined in the stakeholder strategy.

4.2.1 Dissemination for academic community

The SeaClear 2.0 consortium will disseminate the results of the project via open access to scientific periodicals, journals, and repositories such as arXiv and Zenodo. On average, one publication per partner per year is foreseen, for a total of 52+. A publication procedure will be determined to ensure that prior notice is given to the entire partnership allowing any justifiable objections to be raised, discussed, and resolved. Some top journals that we will target in areas relevant to the project are: Control Engineering Practice, IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, Journal of Field Robotics, Underwater Technologies, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Marine Policy, Environmental Systems and Decisions. Some key conferences: IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), IEEE Conference on Decision and Control (CDC), IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML), International Marine Debris Conference (IMDC), OCEANS, EurOcean.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

4.2.2 Dissemination for professional community

The main goal is to draw the attention of the industry to potential applications generated by the project. A key way in which this will be done is via participation at industrial fairs, see Table 8.

TRADE FAIRS (2023 – 2025)	FIELD	EXHIBITING PARTNERS
Oceanology International, Mar 2024, London	Marine and underwater technologies	SST
SMM, Sep 2024, Hamburg	Shipbuilding, marine equipment & tech.	Fraunhofer, TUM, HPA
Posidonia Intl Shipping Exhibit, Jun 2024, Athens	Shipbuilding, marine equipment & tech.	MDAnchor
Euromaritime, Feb 2023, 2024, 2025, Marseille	Advanced ship technologies, clean ports	SST
Ocean Business, Apr 2023&2025, Southampton	Marine and underwater tech.	SST
Metstrade, Nov 2024, Amsterdam	Shipbuilding, marine equipment & tech.	TU Delft, SST
Pollutec, Nov 2023, Lyon	Marine pollution, Recycling	Veolia
SRR, Jun 2025 - Madrid	Recovery and Recycling	TECNOSUB, Veolia
ECOFIRA, Oct 2023, 2024, 2025, Valencia	Environmental Solutions & Ecologic Transition	SST, TECNOSUB
HYDROSESOFT, Feb 2025, Madrid	Sensors & Hydro-Environmental Intl. Symposium	TU Delft, UNIDU

Table 8. Potential fairs in which SeaClear2.0 partners can participate

The consortium will identify any specific R&D in the SeaClear2.0 project that can be aligned with or benefit from external projects and will be contacted for establishing R&D cooperation. This includes projects that are funded either publicly or otherwise by companies. The communication may result in an information exchange or research collaboration. The details of the cooperation initiatives will be discussed and decided in the General Assembly. The project will link to other projects through the networks and expertise provided by the advisory board members. The project's open project publications (deliverables) will also be shared with these projects and other relevant industry stakeholders to further disseminate information about the project.

The partnership will organize industry/end-user events at demonstration/pilot sites, which will be replicated through the cascade funding. At these events, potential end-users of the project will be invited to a specific session, in which the technical project partners will present the SeaClear2.0 technology, and its potential for use, while they will be able to see a live demonstration of the technology, followed by a Q&A session.

4.2.3 Dissemination for policy community

Policy community dissemination is a really important part of project dissemination, aiming at project area decision-makers, making feasible changes according to project results, by providing evidence for

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

new legislation and the implementation of existing regulations to achieve good environmental status and accelerating the uptake of SeaClear 2.0 solutions by demonstrating its scalability and replicability.

The aim of engaging policy and decision-makers in the project is to develop policy recommendations and share policy-relevant outcomes and outputs with those charged with turning them into practice, at the local, national, and EU level. This will be achieved through the decision-making workshops that the project will implement at the demonstration/pilot/replication sites, through the drafting of a White Paper that the project will deliver to key decision-makers, and through the final Policy Roundtable. The project will also participate/present at relevant policy events by other projects/initiatives, national-level events, and EU-level.

4.2.4 Communication and Dissemination for general public community

Communication and dissemination for the general public community is the widest possible way of dispersing project results and goals, primarily via digital channels and project digital tools, such as project website and social media. We expect that maintaining the interesting basis of digital communication will consequentially cause interest from various relevant media and TV companies and result in the project being presented on TV appearances, media portals, etc., which will be highly attractive to the general public of the project area.

Public outreach and engagement activities will be implemented throughout the whole project duration. Community activation events at the demonstration/pilot sites and the associated regions will be a key way through which to share information about the project and involve the local communities in project activities. These events will include a range of activities including community beach clean-ups, and other outreach events, such as for example upcycled art exhibitions, and photography exhibitions, and will aim to educate and build capacity on measures to address marine litter in the local community. The creation of Communities of Practice will also be fostered at each of the demo/pilot sites and associated regions to ensure the longevity of project impacts and the continuation of initiated actions.

4.2.5 Dissemination for associated regions community

To support accelerated uptake of our solutions, dissemination activities will proactively target associated regions to enable them to closely follow the project and its demonstrations. Relevant deliverables and best practices will be shared with the associated regions, and they will also be invited to travel to demonstration events.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

4.3 Communication and Dissemination timeline

The project communication and dissemination timeline are presented in Tables 9 – 12, one table for each implementation year. The tables will be monitored and updated every 6 months.

YEAR 1 - Projected Dates														
Dissemination Activity	Target number	Location	Month											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
			M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Publications in scientific journals and conference proceedings	52+	TBC												
Conference / Congress participation	8 [2/Ac. partner]	TBC												
Links with other Missions, Projects and Initiatives (relates to Policy)	3	TBC												
Cooperation/connection with other actions/projects (relates to dissemination, outreach, and knowledge transfer)	4													
Call to Actions in local communities	min.20 [5/year]	Marseille, Tarragona, Dubrovnik, Venice, Ashdod, Hamburg												
Newsletters (Topic: workshop Dubrovnik, website...]	4 [1/year]	N/A										#1		

D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan		
WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5	
Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU	

YEAR 2 - Projected Dates														
Dissemination Activity	Target number	Location	Month											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
			M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Publications in scientific journals and conference proceedings	52+	TBC												
Conference / Congress participation	8 [2/Ac.partner]	TBC												
Links with other Missions, Projects and Initiatives (relates to Policy)	3	TBC												
Cooperation/connection with other actions/projects (relates to dissemination, outreach and knowledge transfer)	4	N/A												
Call for Actions in local communities	min.20 [5 each year]	Marseille, Tarragona, Dubrovnik, Venice, Ashdod, Hamburg												
Newsletters (topic: announce call for AR)	4 [1/yr]	N/A					#2							
Establishment of Communities of Practice (proven by 1st CoP activity)		Marseille, Tarragona, Dubrovnik,												

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

		Venice, Ashdod, Hamburg	■	■	■	■								■
International Boat Show of Venice		Venice						■						
Outreach event 2: 1st competition (schools)		Partner locations									■			

Table 10: Dissemination timeline – Year 2

D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan		
WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination		Version: V1.5
Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)		Level: PU

YEAR 3 - Projected Dates														
Dissemination Activity	Target Number	Location	Month											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
			M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Publications in scientific journals and conference proceedings	52+	TBC												
Conference / Congress participation	8 [2/Ac.partner]	TBC												
Links with other Missions, Projects and Initiatives (relates to Policy)	3	TBC												
Cooperation/connection with other actions/projects (relates to dissemination, outreach and knowledge transfer)	4	N/A												
Call for Actions in local communities	min.20 [5 each year]	Marseille, Tarragona, Dubrovnik, Venice, Ashdod, Hamburg												
Newsletters (Topics: demo and pilot)	4 [1/yr]	N/A												#3
Outreach event 3: details TBC		Tarragona, Dubrovnik, Venice, Hamburg,												

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

		Ashdod, Marseille												
Outreach event at Associated Regions: beach cleanup, workshop & other citizen engagement activities		Associated Regions 1-5												
Marseille Demonstration: - Workshop - Event targeting end-users - Last Marseille event & exhibition (competition results & artistic installation)/outreach event 4		Marseille												
Ashdod Pilot: - Workshop - Event targeting end-users - Last Ashdod event on (competition results & artistic installation)/outreach event 4		Ashdod												
2nd clean-up in associated regions		5 associated regions												
Outreach event 5: 2nd competition (photography)		Partner locations												

Table 11: Dissemination timeline – Year 3

D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan		
WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination		Version: V1.5
Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)		Level: PU

YEAR 4 - Projected Dates														
Dissemination Activity	Target Number	Location	Month											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
			M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48
Publications in scientific journals and conference proceedings	52+	TBC												
Conference / Congress participation	8 [2/Ac.partner]	TBC												
Links with other Missions, Projects and Initiatives (relates to Policy)	3	TBC												
Cooperation/connection with other actions/projects (relates to dissemination, outreach and knowledge transfer)	4	N/A												
Calls to Action in local communities	min.20 [5 each year]	Marseille, Tarragona, Dubrovnik, Venice, Ashdod, Hamburg												
Newsletters (Topic: project outputs)	4 [1/yr]	N/A												#4
2nd cleanup		Marseile & Ashdod												

D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Dubrovnik Neretva Demonstration: - Event targeting end-users - Final event & exhibition (competition results & artistic installation)/outreach event 4 - 2nd cleanup		Dubrovnik												
Venice Pilot: - Workshop - Event targeting end-users - Final event & exhibition (competition results & artistic installation)/outreach event 4 - 2nd cleanup		Venice												
Hamburg Pilot: - Workshop - Event targeting end-users - Final event & exhibition (competition results & artistic installation)/outreach event 4 - 2nd cleanup		Hamburg												

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

Tarragona Demonstration: - Workshop - Event targeting end-users - Final event & exhibition (competition results & artistic installation)/outreach event 4 - 2nd cleanup		Tarragona																
Policy Round Table																		
Policy White Paper																		

Table 12: Dissemination timeline – Year 4

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

5. Summary

Deliverable 6.1 aims at designing the coherent CDSEP document. In order to achieve that, the premise was a detailed analysis of stakeholder groups, and the means to mobilize them, positioning in this way the people, their needs, and interests in the focus of the document. This analysis was followed by specifically tailored communication and dissemination types, channels, and tools. The concept of communities of practice was used as a main tangible tool for stakeholder engagement, with altogether 6 main CoPs and 5 additional CoP groups from associated regions. SeaClear 2.0 CoPs cover the widest possible community groups and assure the inclusion of all interested parties in the project. SeaClear 2.0 communication and dissemination activities are formatted as both educational and inspirational instruments to promote our action and results, also showing how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible. CDSEP is making sure to introduce the project's novel technologies and to influence policy-making, industry, and the scientific community. The evaluation and monitoring of the CDSEP activities are crucial – thus, it will determine the degree to which the project goals and relevant KPIs have been reached and the relationship between the outcomes and the efforts made to reach the above-mentioned. The communication and dissemination plan, as a set of quantitative and qualitative indicators, will provide the monitoring of the successful deployment in terms of efficiency and effectiveness of communication and dissemination activities. This construct will help the project to better understand the barriers to efficacious communication and will serve to refine the communication and dissemination activities accordingly and timely as planned for every 6 months.

 101093822	D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan	
	WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination	Version: V1.5
	Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)	Level: PU

6. References

- [1] Dodds F., Benson E. (CIVICUS, Johannesburg) – Multistakeholder Dialogues Toolkit (2010)
- [2] Kvam R. under the direction of Ronza C. (Environmental and Social Safeguards Unit at the Inter-American Development Bank) – Meaningful stakeholder engagement - A Joint Publication of the Multilateral Financial Institutions Group on Environmental and Social Standards (2019)
- [3] Newcombe R. (Department of Construction Management & Engineering the University of Reading, Whiteknights) - From client to project stakeholders: a stakeholder mapping approach (1999)
- [4] Mercieca B. (University of Southern Queensland; Toowoomba, Queensland, Australia) – What Is a Community of Practice? (2017)
- [5] Wenger E. (Cambridge University; Cambridge, United Kingdom) – Communities of Practice: Learning, Meaning, and Identity (1998)
- [6] Wegner E., McDermott R., Snyder W. (Harvard Business Press - Harvard Business Review Notice of Use Restrictions) – Cultivating Communities of Practice (2002)
- [7] H2020 Programme Guidance, Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects, Version 1.1, 07 January 2020

101093822

D6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Plan

WP6: Public engagement, policy, dissemination

Version: V1.5

Author(s): I. Pozniak (DUNEA), D. Orthodoxou (ISOTECH), D. Kallitsi (ISOTECH)

Level: PU